

Spectrophotometric Study on Copper-sulphosalicylic Acid Chelate

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The 1:1 chelate formed between Cu(II) and sulphosalicylic acid has been investigated by spectrophotometry. The stability constants have been determined at different pHs, ionic strengths, and temperatures. From the temperature coefficient of the stability constant, ΔS and ΔH for the chelation reaction have been calculated. The thermodynamic stability constant has been determined by different methods of extrapolation.

The olive-green chelate, formed by the interaction of copper ion and sulphosalicylic acid, has been studied by various workers in the field. Spacu and Macarovic¹ suggested a composition $[\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{CO}_2\text{SO}_3)_2]\text{H}_4^+$ for the complex. Turner and Anderson² determined the stability constant of the 1:1 chelate at pH 5.0. Lasater and Anderson³ in connection with their studies on aluminium-sulphosalicylate chelate, using copper chelate as an 'indicator', determined the stability constant of the latter at pH 4.1. Subsequently Vasil'ev and Gorokhovskii⁴ made a polarographic study of copper-sulphosalicylate chelate at a pH range of 7 to 10. Singh and Banks⁵ determined the stability constants of the complexes formed between Cu^{2+} and sulphosalicylic acid by pH-titration method. More recently Nair⁶ studied the system by spectrophotometry and determined the stability constants of the 1:1 chelate at different pHs.

None of the earlier workers attempted to determine the thermodynamic properties. Besides, most of them used copper sulphate in their works. The observations of Monk *et al.*,⁷ and others show that copper sulphate is incompletely dissociated in solution, and hence unsuitable for the purpose. We have therefore used copper perchlorate. In the present work thermodynamic properties like ΔF , ΔH , and ΔS , associated with the formation of the complex, have been determined.

EXPERIMENTAL

The experimental details are similar to those described in our earlier publications⁸

1. *Bull. Soc. Stiintje Oluj*, 1936, 8, 364.
2. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 912.
3. *Ibid.*, 1952, 74, 1459.
4. *Chem. Abs.*, 1956, 52, 6925^d.
5. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 81, 6159; *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1960, 15, 125.
6. *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1961, 57, 1988.
7. *Ibid.*, 1956, 52, 816.
8. Aditya *et al.*, *this Journal*, 1969, 36, 473; 1960, 37, 557; 1961, 38, 19.

DISCUSSION

Absorption spectra of copper perchlorate and a mixture of copper perchlorate and the ligand show that these are almost co-incident at low pHs, but at higher pHs (4.0 or above) these are separated, suggesting complex formation. The chelation reaction between Cu^{2+} and sulphosalicylic acid is therefore pH-dependent.

Molecular Composition.—Job's method of continued variation⁹ was applied for the determination of molecular composition of the complex at pH 4.5. Plots of $\bar{D}$ (difference between the optical density of a solution of copper perchlorate and sulphosalicylic acid and that of a solution containing no sulphosalicylic acid) against mole fraction provided maxima at positions corresponding to 1:1 composition of the metal ion and the ligand. Fig. 1 shows Job's curves at 750 μ , corresponding to total molarities of $9.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ and $1.2 \times 10^{-2} M$. The same has been carried out at other wave lengths (the curves are not shown). All of them indicate the complex to be of 1:1 type in acidic solutions.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

Extinction Coefficient.—Extinction coefficients of copper perchlorate at 750 μ and at pH 4.0 and 4.5 were reported in our earlier communications⁸. The same for the complex have also been determined in a similar manner by measuring the absorbances at 750 μ of solutions of different concentrations of copper perchlorate and sulphosalicylic acid, taken in large excess and pH adjusted at 4.0 and 4.5. The values of extinction coefficients of the complex, using 750 μ , are 36.57 (± 0.29) and 33.63 (± 0.27) at pH 4.0 and 4.5, respectively.

Stability Constant.—The stability constant of the complex:

$$K = \frac{[\text{Complex}]}{\{[\text{Cu}^{2+}]_{\text{total}} - [\text{Complex}]\} \{[\text{S.S.A.}]_{\text{total}} - [\text{Complex}]\}}$$

has been calculated as in our earlier publications⁸ at different pHs and ionic strengths.

Table I records the results at pH 4.0 and 4.5 and at different ionic strengths. At pH 4.5 stability constants were determined for ionic strengths 0.02, 0.08, 0.12, 0.2, and 0.5, whereas at pH 4.0 it was determined at 0.2 ionic strength only. The stability constant decreases with an increase in the ionic strength of the medium, with exception to the result at $\mu=0.5$.

TABLE I

Wave length = 750 m μ .		Cell width = 3 cm.	
Ionic strength.	No. of readings taken with diff. concs. of reactants.	Average value of stability const. $\times 10^{-2}$.	
0.20	6 (at pH 4.0 & at 24°)	1.07 (± 0.02)	
0.02	8 (at pH 4.5 & at 26°)	3.68 (± 0.32)	
0.08	8 (")	3.18 (± 0.24)	
0.12	10 (")	2.87 (± 0.22)	
0.20	6 (")	2.50 (± 0.27)	
0.50	8 (")	2.51 (± 0.27)	

The product of the stability constant at $\mu=0.2$ and the H^+ -ion concentration of the solution are nearly constant at both the pHs. At pH 4.5, 0.2 ionic strength, and 28°, the value of $K(H^+)$ is 0.8×10^{-2} . $K(H^+)$ for pH 4.0 and same ionic strength and temperature is 1.005×10^{-2} (the value of K at 28° is taken from the plot of $\log K$ against $1/T$). The two values are nearly the same, suggesting that the chelation reaction involves liberation of one proton as shown below.

Since various workers have studied the same system, it would be interesting to compare the different results. Turner and Anderson⁹ report a value of 5×10^3 for the stability constant:

$$\left(K = \frac{[CuR^-]}{[Cu^{2+}][HR^{2-}]} \right)$$

at pH 5.0 and 25°. Lasater and Anderson⁹ report a value of $K=4.54 \times 10^3$ at pH 4.1 and 30°, which seems to be nearly equal to the value at pH 5.0. In such reactions, where protons are liberated, the value of K , as represented in the above equation, is very unlikely to be the same at pH 4.1 and 5.0. It appears therefore that at least one of the results may be erroneous. It seems that the value at pH 5.0, reported by Turner and Anderson⁹, may be more correct as $K(H^+)$ ($=0.5 \times 10^{-2}$), which should be independent of pH, is of the same order as reported by us (0.8×10^{-2} at pH 4.5 and $\mu=0.2$). A quantitative comparison between our result and those of Turner and Anderson⁹ is not possible as these are at different ionic strengths. Further, some discrepancies in the results of Lasater and Anderson⁹ have been pointed out by Nanda and Aditya¹⁰. They have disagreed with the value of the stability constant of aluminium sulphosalicylate complex, reported by Lasater and Anderson from displacement measurements, using copper-sulphosalicylate chelate as 'indicator'. If the value of the stability constant of copper chelate be incorrect, that of aluminium-chelate will also be incorrect.

As regards the results of Singh and Banks⁵, they report a value of $\log K' = 9.52$ at 25° and 0.1 ionic strength for the 1:1 chelate. K' is represented as

$$K' = \frac{[\text{CuR}^-]}{[\text{R}^{3-}][\text{Cu}^{2+}]}$$

where R^{3-} stands for $-\text{O}_3\text{S} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_3 \cdot \text{O}^- \cdot \text{COO}^-$. This form of stability constant, which is independent of pH , is related to K by the expression $K [\text{H}^+]/K_d$ (K_d is the dissociation constant of the phenolic group of the ligand). The value of $\log K'$, obtained from our result at 0.1 ionic strength, is 9.95 at 28° (the value of K_d is 10^{-13} , taken from the results of Singh and Banks⁵). There seems to be a slight difference in the values of $\log K'$ reported by Singh and Banks and ours. They used copper sulphate which might have slightly vitiated their result.

A comparison of our result can be made with that of Nair⁶. The values of $\log K'$, reported⁷ by him, are 10.03, 9.65, and 9.49 at pH 4.03, 5.1, and 5.5, respectively, at 25° and 0.2 ionic strength. The values of the same ($\log K'$) from the present measurements are 9.92 and 9.82 at pH 4.0 and 4.5 and at the same temperature and ionic strength.

A comparison of our work with that of Vasil'ev and Gorokhovskii⁴ is not possible, as they made a polarographic study of the complex at pH range 7–10 where 1:2 complex is more likely to exist in solution.

Thermodynamic Stability Constant.—The thermodynamic stability constant of the complex was determined by different methods of extrapolations. Plots of $\log K$ against μ and $\mu^{\frac{1}{2}}$ provided non-linear curves. Plot of $\log K$ against $\mu^{\frac{1}{2}}$ is, however, linear.

In the Hitchcock type of extrapolation¹¹, using the Davies equation¹²,

$$\log K + 7A \frac{\sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}}$$

should provide a straight line on plotting against μ . This, however, was nonlinear, but when it was plotted against $\mu^{\frac{1}{2}}$, a straight line was obtained. The values of $\log K_T$, obtained by different extrapolations, are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Type of plot.	Log K_T at pH 4.5.
$\log K$ against μ	2.71
$\log K$ against $\mu^{\frac{1}{2}}$	2.69
$\log K$ against $\mu^{\frac{1}{4}}$	2.75
$\log K + 7A \frac{\sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}}$ against μ	2.85
$\log K + 7A \frac{\sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}}$ against $\mu^{\frac{1}{2}}$	2.84

Entropy and Enthalpy Changes.—In view of the difficulty in obtaining the thermodynamic stability constant, we have determined the entropy and enthalpy changes at a

11. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 50, 2076.

12. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 2093.

fixed ionic strength. The stability constant at pH 4.0 and $\mu=0.2$ was determined at 20° and 40° in addition to that at the room temperature (34°) (Table III). From the slope of the plot of $\log K$ against $1/T$ (Fig. 2), the value of ΔH is 2.10 (± 0.2) kcal. ΔS for the formation of the complex is 16.3 (± 1) e.u.

TABLE III

pH = 4.0. Wave length = 750m μ . Call width = 1 cm. Ionic strength = 0.2.			
Temp.	No. of readings with diff. concs. of reactants.	Average stability const.	ΔF (= $-RT \ln K$). (kcal.)
20°	5	$0.922(\pm 0.01) \times 10^4$	-2.63(± 0.01)
34°	6	$1.070(\pm 0.02) \times 10^4$	-2.85(± 0.01)
40°	5	$1.160(\pm 0.02) \times 10^4$	-2.96 (± 0.01)

The values of the thermodynamic functions show that the stability of the complex is mainly due to the entropy increase.

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